

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PSYCHOSOMATICS, ITS CAUSES AND CORRECTION MECHANISMS

G. Efendiyeva

head teacher of the department

of general psychology

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2366-0872>

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Abstract

Psychosomatics (from ancient Greek Ψυχή - soul and σῶμα - body), psychosomatic medicine - a direction in medical psychology that studies the influence of psychological factors on the occurrence, course, outcome of somatic (physical) diseases, the area of disciplinary research of psychosomatic problems - research aimed to study the interaction between mind and body, a branch of clinical psychology. The subject of research in psychosomatics as a science is the psychological factors in the occurrence and course of diseases. According to representatives of psychosomatic medicine, in the 21st century, about half of diseases are psychogenic in nature. Mental factors not only provoke some diseases, but also influence the course of many diseases.

Keywords: psychosomatic development, management, feelings, psychologist, psychotherapy, correction, emotions, trauma, illness, treatment, consultation.

Introduction:

There is a popular opinion in society that all human diseases arise due to psychological disorders that arise in the soul, in the subconscious, in the thoughts of a person. The idea that every disease has its own mystical (symbolic) cause is a common misconception. Somatic diseases caused by psychogenic factors are called "psychosomatic disorders". In human medicine, the influence of somatic diseases on the psyche is also studied. Experts in evidence-based medicine define psychosomatic disorders as illnesses that arise or worsen due to stress. The idea of the influence of psychological factors on health is very ancient. Reflections on this topic can already be found in Hippocrates and Aristotle. Plato wrote about this in the dialogue "Charmides, or On Prudence" [2].

Just as one should not try to treat the eyes separately from the head and the head separately from the body, so one should not treat the body without treating the soul, and Hellenic doctors had failures in treating many diseases when they did not recognize the need to take care of the whole, but meanwhile, if the whole is in bad condition, then the part cannot be in order... everything - both good and bad - is generated in the body and in the whole person by the soul, and it is from it that everything stems, just as in the eyes everything stems from the head. That is why you must first and foremost treat the soul if you want your head and the rest of your body to feel good. The soul, my dear, must be treated with well-known spells, the latter being nothing more than true speeches: from these speeches, prudence takes root in the soul, and its rooting and presence facilitate the introduction of health both in the area of the head and in the area of the whole body.

Methodology:

The term "psychosomatic" was introduced in 1818 by the German physician Johann Christian Heinroth. In 1822, the German psychiatrist Carl Jacobi introduced the concept of "somatopsychic," meaning the opposite

and at the same time a complement to the relationship to "psychosomatic." However, only a century later this term became generally accepted in medical practice, mainly thanks to psychoanalytic psychologists; during this era, psychosomatic therapy was sometimes called "applied psychoanalysis in medicine" [1].

In particular, Sigmund Freud, together with Joseph Breuer, proposed that repressed emotions and mental trauma, through a defense mechanism called "conversion," could manifest themselves in the form of somatic symptoms. Freud pointed out that this requires the so-called "somatic readiness" - a physical factor that is important for the "choice of the organ" in which the disease will manifest itself

Main part:

Psychoanalysts Helen Deutsch (English), Helen Dunbar and Franz Alexander, who emigrated to the United States in the forties, drew attention to the study of psychosomatic problems. By the end of the 50s, about 5,000 articles about somatic medicine from the point of view of psychologists had been published in the American scientific literature. Also such famous analysts as Alfred Adler and Leopold Szondi worked in this area. In Russia, scientists from the school of I.P. Pavlov worked in this direction, in connection with the development of the method of experimental neurosis [3].

Stress mobilizes the body: adrenaline and norepinephrine are released, blood vessels constrict, blood circulation accelerates, bronchi dilate, but food digestion stops: in tense moments it is not needed. When the danger has passed, these processes stop and the body quickly returns to normal functioning. Therefore, one-time stress is not so dangerous.

But if a stressful situation lasts for a long time, the body continues to work in danger mode. Its organs and systems wear out: the heart and blood vessels, the endocrine system, the digestive and respiratory organs.

A resident of a big city has enough reasons to be stressed. A person gets used to many factors: constant noise, crowded people, traffic jams. Researchers also note that the cause of chronic stress can be both extremely traumatic events such as the loss of a loved one, and an ongoing stream of non-dramatic life and work problems [4;5].

It has been proven that, in combination with other factors, chronic stress can lead to the development of atherosclerosis, irritable bowel syndrome, chronic pain syndrome, as well as weaken the immune system and cognitive function. Mental problems change your lifestyle, and this affects the state of your body. Thus, with depression, a person may lead a less healthy lifestyle: abuse alcohol and overeat in the hope of lifting his mood, neglect physical activity and refuse to take medications because of his gloomy moods.

Conclusions:

But the deterioration of physical health occurs not only due to social-behavioral factors, but also due to biological ones - in no way dependent on human actions. For example, due to hormonal imbalances characteristic of depression, various systems and organs suffer. Patients with depression are more likely to develop coronary heart disease, and with existing angina, depression increases the risk of myocardial infarction and cardiac arrest by almost three times. People with depression have poorer recovery rates after a heart attack. Studies have also found a connection between depression and the development of type 2 diabetes and osteoporosis.

Actually, if we talk in general about the psychological support of people with psychosomatic disorders, then, first of all, it is still necessary to carry out a differential diagnosis and make sure that the disorder does not have an unambiguous explanation from the functioning of the body. For example, when providing psychotherapeutic support to people suffering from depression, it makes sense to check the functioning of the endocrine and cardiovascular systems. Given that some endocrine diseases (autoimmune thyroiditis) can cause metabolic disorders, this can lead to symptoms characteristic of depression. Also, incorrect functioning of the adrenal glands, causing excessive releases of cortisol with insufficient amounts of dopamine, can cause conditions that can be called depressive. Despite the fact that depression is not a classic psychosomatic disease, it can be of an organic nature, and the correct compensated functioning of internal organs can largely reduce or completely eliminate the symptoms characteristic of depression [5].

However, many symptoms have both primary - obvious - and secondary - non-obvious - benefits. They can be psychological, social and existential. In the process of psychotherapy, it is important to understand what benefits a particular disease brings for a particular person. This will affect not only the causes of occurrence, but also the healing process. For example, as a

result of cancer, a person could begin to receive attention from family and colleagues; They began to sympathize with him and treat him in a special way, the way he always wanted. It is likely that the healing process will be slower than usual because secondary benefits in the form of a desired attitude may get in the way. In addition, in the absence of attention, a person is faced with symbolic dying, which could become the psychological cause of a deadly disease: internal and perhaps even unconscious experiences thus received a completely organic expression [4;6].

Also, the psychotherapeutic process can address the underlying causes of a particular disease. That is, the study of a person's early age, his experiences, his characteristic emotions and the processes of overcoming the main stages of development can provide the key to understanding the causes of a particular dysfunction. It is known that various kinds of fixations at certain stages of psychosexual development can lead to hypertension, anorexia, and alcoholism. Of course, not all of the above, again, is a psychosomatic disorder, but this once again proves that the early stages of development and traumatic situations are extremely important when analyzing disorders in the functioning of the body and psyche.

In general, the task of psychological counseling in the case of a psychosomatic illness is to help a person understand the essence of his illness and what lies behind it, as well as to help develop a normal way of cognitive, behavioral and psycho-emotional manifestation instead of the maladaptive one that led him to a psychosomatic illness [7;8].

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